

Reviews In Cross-Border Logistics; Problems And Contribution Toward The Global Supply Chain

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 10, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: November 11, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Cross-Border Logistics, Supply Chain, Global Supply Chain</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5679077</p>	<p><i>A high level of the economy, competition around the world has forced the business companies to compete in offering goods or services. It based on the respond to the needs of consumers with the best offerings under the times and expenses gaps. The revolution of the situation in each era has driven organizations to increase their capability to manage internal and external expectations together for organizational achievement. Therefore, cross-border logistics is one significant operation of all activities in term of logistics functions. This is to ensure for better trades between countries where the point of origin to final destination are formulated. The research indicates that the problems occurring in the global supply chain concern cross-border operations, logistics service providers and government administration. The most mentioned issue involved processes at the border area, especially for trading performed by logistics service providers and government administration. These reviews were established on the components of effective operations for global supply chain contribution including electronic processing system, infrastructure development and improvement of customs inspection.</i></p>

Introduction

The business has been competing for days now to take advantage of the opportunities to offer goods or services that respond to the needs of consumers with the best offerings under the organization's time and expense gap. At the same time, new generation customers expect to be provided and be satisfied by what they need. Most of them alternatively decide based on information, their own experiences and other's experiences in various choices. Therefore, internal administration and management's efficiency and effectiveness in responding to consumers' needs should be focused on.

Many modern management tools and modern business strategies are concerned about supporting organizational performance and fulfilling customer requirements. Some business concentrates on marketing perspectives as the concept of marketing mixes is well known as tools used for effectiveness and smoothly running business operations among high competition organizations. For example, the retail mix has always been applied to work closely with customers (Blut, Teller & Floh, 2018) or innovative technologies to lead customer recognition of their shopping experiences (Foroudi, Gupta, Sivarajah & Broderick, 2018). Even though numerous businesses are doing well in offering products or services to meet customer's expectations, some still have faced uncontrollable cost, limited resources and a slow adaptation to the changes of business environments which make them finally fail in the end.

The revolution of the situation in each era has forced organizations to increase their capability to manage internal and external expectations together for organizational accomplishment. It also can be said that vendors or service providers need to have good practices in every process and procedure, from upstream to downstream, where products and services are delivered to consumers. The risk of the supply chain was mentioned in previous decades as "Supply Chain Risk". It has been enormously concentrated in academia and the industry because globalization and outsourcing are currently well known to regularly lead to a huge broadcast "Supply Chain Structure" among different countries and continents. (Chung, Talluri & Kovacs, 2018). Similarly to the present that "the concept of supply chain management" is also widely in attention for every business and become necessary tools for value creation. Also, the companies can improve both the organizational environment and their cost performance by implementing logistics practices from upstream to downstream in the supply chain (Graham, Graham & Holt, 2018). The understanding of supply chain management can benefit the organization from cost structure analysis (Ongkunaruk & Piyakarn, 2011) and improve operating efficiencies in terms of cost reduction using third party or outsourcing strategy implementation (Kumar et al., 2013).

The concept of supply chain management is an essential factor for companies recently and has been widely applied in every industry, including in the construction company. The supply chain consists of all firms

and organizations which contribute delivery of a high-quality project or service to the project owner (Benton & McHenry, 2010).

On the other hand, a high level of the economy, competition around the world, and the concept of "Economic Integration" has begun to seek agreements and approaches to increase potential and stability among countries in a geographic region (Pengman & Kettapan, 2018). Consequently, many researchers have studied to improve all procedures and capabilities with all concerned parties for trading. The organization then becomes involved in global operations. The logistical components are considered to minimize cost and provide an acceptable level of service to customers (Stock & Lambert, 2001) to reach a competitive advantage.

Doan and Xing (2018) found the factors influencing trade efficiency, which is the establishment of Free trade agreements (FTAs) including ASEAN, EU, NAFTA that made the country become a more valuable economy and also contributes positively to the efficiency of exports with the countries among the regional countries. Those factors consist of the rules of origin (ROO), represented as significant barriers undercutting the efficiency, the Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) that plays an essential role in the promotion of exports and enhance export volume, which is similar to the findings of Mohmand, Salman, Mughal, Imran, and Makarevic (2015), found six major factors affecting the export environment which are 1) GDP; theoretically it is assumed that larger the country size, the more it would trade. So if two countries have larger GDP, their trade would be higher. 2) Distance: captures transportation cost between the two countries. Greater distance would mean greater transportation cost. 3) Regional Trade Agreement (RTA): Trade Agreement is bolstering trade. 4) Religion and Language that concerned cultural influence for both trading countries and 5) Border: Countries with the shared border have higher chances of stronger bilateral trade relations.

Therefore, the low level of limitation in cross-border operations usually positively impacts the trading. The cross-border area has been considered as a source of opportunity, too (Slusarciuc, 2015). Potential accessibility and border effects have been explained as variables affecting market potential as well. For example, the improvement of road infrastructure should encourage more productive inaccessibility for border crossing, and the increase of consolidation of the single market would also enlarge the market potential (Salas-Olmedo, García & Gutiérrez, 2015).

In the context of trade logistics, logistics performance is an important aspect that determines a country's competence in facilitating domestic and international trade (Stock & Lambert, 2001). Thus, cross-border logistics is one significant operation of all activities in terms of logistics functions to make a more straightforward trade between the countries where is the point of origin to the destination where the end-users are located. Therefore, this article aims to explain how is cross-border logistics important in the global supply chain. The concept and the importance of global supply chain and cross-border logistics from previous studies will be first described to show a clear picture of the global trade operations related to the contemporary situation. Then, there will be an explanation of problems and the enhancement of cross-border logistics towards the global supply chain, which would be advantages to worldwide business and logistics planning for practitioners. Finally, this research will be summed up with the limitation and conclusion of the study, which provide the academician to develop the productive approach for enhancing the opportunities of trading among cross-border.

2. Global Supply Chain

2.1 Concept of Supply chain

Many academicians defined the concept and advantages of supply chain management differently, for instance, flexibility, speed and empirical abilities (Stock & Lambert, 2001).

Several important differences exist between the above definition of supply chain management and the council of logistics management's description of logistics. First and foremost, supply chain management is the management of eight key business processes including, customer relationship management, customer service management, demand management, order fulfilment, manufacturing flow management, procurement, product development and commercialization, returns

The management of goods and services from the raw materials to the product delivery at the end user is related to a broad spectrum of functional areas. Supply Chain Management associated with activities like inbound, outbound transportation or lodging warehouse, inventory control, sourcing procuring and supply management, forecasting production planning and scheduling, ordered process and customer services. Supply chain management includes all those related to the movement of goods from the raw materials stage through the end users/customers (Choudhary et al., 2018).

How a product is manufactured and the new service offerings have changed significantly to provide the company with the goal of satisfying consumer demands with the best value when accepting the order from consumers, instead of putting the original product on the market without buying order. The dimension of the divergence on consumer behaviour brings the marketers to focus on adding value to the products and services to achieve the highest satisfaction from the consumer. Due to that, the concept of "Value Chain" developed by Michale E. Porter from the book named Competitive Advantage was well-known and accepted as management

tools. It helps to understand creating value of product and services towards customers from the first step until finished products are launched.

Principles of the Value Chain are different Supply Chains. Supply chain management emphasizes raw material management or resources within the organization that create maximum efficiency from the beginning of the process until the consumer receives the product or uses the service. While the value chain concept focuses on delivering value to the consumer in every process, starting from raw materials intake to the end of the supply chain process, strategic management is always concerned.

The above importance of the value chain theory and concept motivates many organizations and other related institutes interested in spread studying to add value to products and services throughout the supply chain. For instance, the tourism industry, which creates customer satisfaction by increasing value from tour operators as pre-delivery support and in the process of tourism delivery, the value is enhanced by transporters and third parties, such as hotels and travel agents who carry travel packages as post-delivery support (Yilmaz & Bititci, 2006). In the manufacturing industry, the value chain analysis is a must because it's increasing value for the customer and the positive effect of relationship marketing perspective. (Song, Chatterjee & Jia 2015), additionally, value-adding up in backward stages provide well maintained in functional business development, for example, research and development, value delivery in the marketplace, management information system, branding perceived, financial perspective and customer service after sales to strengthen the value creation of the product in marketing (Yang, Luo, Li, Yang, & Lee, 2013).

Figure 1 represents the explanation from Michael Porter's view, who mentions five generic classifications of primary activities concerned with the competition in the industry.

These functions can be separated into a list of particular parts depending on the appropriate distribution and the company's strategies. The description of these categories can be speculated as follows (McGee, 2014):

(1) "Inbound logistics" is the work activities required to receive, store, and disseminate right to the products, for example, material carrying, warehouse management and stock or inventory management, et cetera.

(2) "Operations" concerns every function in transforming the inputs into the outputs and the effective implementation of value-added, which can be done from product machining, package design, assembly system, service, experimentation, and so on.

Figure 1
The generic value chain
Source: Porter (1985).

(3) "Outbound logistics" refers to all activities associated with collecting, storing and physical distribution for the output. It is significant elements to either generate value or develop differentiation. Numerous companies take this activity to operate along with distribution strategies as it is proved that outbound logistics is a primary source of competitive advantage. Significantly, there is a recognition that more than half of value creation for most business appears nearby the final consumer.

(4) "Marketing and sales" are functions concerned with communicating products and services of the company to the target customers, motivating them to purchase by sales representatives, advertisement and sales promotion, and so on.

(5) "Service" refers to the definition to enhance the features of the tangible products by way of contributions to the next buying, for example, providing after-sales service, product repair, et cetera

The upper section in the second part of the value chain associates in all administrative functions (identified support activities) necessary for the business. There are labelled as four components, including "human resource management", "technology development", and "procurement". Those are explained in more details as below;

(1) "Procurement" involves the intake of materials for processing whole activities. Even if this is under the authority of the department of purchasing, almost every staff in the company has a role in purchasing some resources. The procurement usually is taken low cost while there can be a lot of impact on the firms.

(2) "Human resource management" refers to the acquisition of policies, practices, and systems required to influence employees' behaviour, attitude, and performance. (Noe, Hollenbeck, Gerhart&Wright 2014) Its functions consist of recruitment, training and human development, rewarding system, and authorizing the staff in the firm.

(3) "Technology development" is associated with the media, operating systems, electronic devices, practical skills, and others that used by the organization to transform inputs to outputs. There can be categorized into two types. Firstly, "scientific" which concerned with the skills needed. Secondly, "artistic" which are not generally perceived due to those are implemented to support limited activities of the firm, for example, "accounting", "procurement", and so on. In addition, the results may connect to an essential element in adding more value.

(4) "Firm infrastructure" has a huge concern to many functions consisting of essential management, organization plan, finance, legal, external association, and so on, which encourage the implementation of operational aspect along the "value chain".

2.2 Concept of Global Value Chain

The pattern of the production process in the world products has changed into the distribution of separated production in small parts achieving maximum efficiency in various countries. Such practices exist in the products and in services that create value-added on the chain (Office of Industrial Economics, 2014). The more separation emerges, the Global Production Networks or Global Value Chains face relentless competitive pressure to enhance customer value. Various business strategies have also been concentrated in every firm for effectiveness in global distribution (Bhantnagar & Teo, 2009).

The idea of doing things primarily in one country has been changed. Although it used to be, nowadays a unit of finished goods is generally the outputs produced by numerous countries. The value is added in each activity from the beginning to the end of making the product. During producing goods in the global value chain (GVCs), countries trade the products or services and deal with the procedure and connect works. Therefore, the importance of product and service imports is certainly similar to product and service exports to be successful GVCs. (The World Bank, 2019).

The strategic business used to create value in each activity that can be built before the beginning of the supply chain is a clear understanding of the customer's value to start sourcing and to produce the product or service to respond to them. Throughout the supply chain in each activity, the cost must be minimized with maximum value. Customer's value can create those product and service attributes, value delivery, value communication, value production, value proposition, assets and core competencies and value objective and strategy. Creating value in the supply chain is controlled by logistics management, which implements the effective movement and storage of related information, goods, and services from origin to destination.

Consequently, consideration and paying attention to the value creation in every process would lead the business to be successful among the high competition in responding to customer needs and returning enough value in the organization management. Although the companies have varying patterns in offering different products and services, they implement entirely based on the loop of the supply chain with various strategies used to manage sub-activities to create value to consumers.

Figure 2 explained the cooperation of the concerned organization along the supply chain of the organic coffee industry. Figure 2 also presented the activities flow in the chain, which most happened cross-border. The more activities, the more opportunities to have problem and cost. Development of performance of cross-border logistics, therefore bring more competitive advantage in among regional areas.

There are numerous parties and complexities of operations before the product will be delivered to the final customer. Therefore, the global supply chain is sometimes not about the flow of finished goods, the operational process of importing raw materials and input components tax-free, and then exporting finished products assembled from the raw materials and parts, or it's called processing trade (Kang, Park, Yang & Haney, 2018). It is about the overall supply chain. Therefore, effective and efficient flows of such materials, information and payments among supply chain partners play a vital role in implementing the processing trade. The performance of operational cross-border is concerned as a place where the goods or materials are inspected and allowed to flow.

Figure 2
The chain of green coffee model (PSP: processing service provider)

Source : Claro and Claro, 2004

3. Cross-Border Logistics

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logistics

processes influence almost every circadian rhythm of human activity, directly or indirectly. The significant impact logistics has on society, industries, organizations and individuals. Many academicians determine the definition involving logistics as follow;

Kotler and Killer (2015) identified that logistics is defined as "planning, implementing and controlling the physical flow of material and finished goods from the point of origin to the end of use to meet customer's need at a profit.

Stock and Lambert (2001) stated that logistics management is part of the supply chain process that plans, implements, and controls the efficient, adequate flow and storage of goods, services and related information from point-of-origin to point-of-consumption meet customers' requirement. This definition includes the flow of goods, services and information in both the manufacturing and service sectors.

In the context of border crossing, the operations in this area are few pieces of a whole system of logistics activities as its roles are a place of making product flows where both opportunities and threats could come at the same time (Slusarciuc, 2016). Such as, the border area has a significant potential for knowledge transfer, but it also faces substantial barriers under international standards that are inflexible. Moreover, smooth and efficient movement of all resources (goods, services and information) in cross-border operations would maximize organizations' success.

4. Problems of Cross-border Logistics

Business logistics are vital because materials flow into the nation's manufacturing capacity through the logistical process, and finished products are distributed to consumers. The recent growth in global commerce has also expanded the size and complexities of logistic operations (Bowersox, Closs, Cooper, & Bowersox, 2013). Therefore, the operational cross-border is one element of the global supply chain that makes a business successful. Still, the operation implementing there might not go smooth as it would be. The following results are previous research concerning cross-border logistics function that reveals an overall problematic area in cross-border logistics.

The continuing rise of world trade and the desire of many countries to speed up the pace of integration within global trading reflect that logistical achievement in a low and middle-income group of countries is at lower levels than the high-income countries (Gani, 2017). The government has always considered macroeconomics because the government plays a big part in supporting cross-border trade throughout the supply chain, such as the efficiency of the customs clearance process and quality of trade and transport-related infrastructure that the government sector should implement provide.

Although the government may not directly cause border logistics problems, the government sector must foster up the trade and invest in development and promote economic activities occurring in the business

supply chain to be more efficient, more convenient, and faster to achieve a competitive advantage. At Beitbridge Border Post, the governments have come to understand the critical nature of the border crossing and the need to improve with numerous projects and campaigns launched, such as the building of a new bridge across the Limpopo river, which would reduce traffic congestion and significant improvements in physical infrastructure on the Zimbabwean side (Trademark Southern Africa, 2011).

In terms of investment, the ownership in cross-border acquisitions (CBAs) is associated with the government. There are three components under governmental authority that support the effect of the ownership in CBAs consisting of institutional distance, knowledge access (Ex: business knowledge access, country knowledge access) and support from the government, for example, financial matters, participation of stock and the ties of politic which means that government has both directive and indirect effect on ownership received by customers (Pinto, Ferreira, Falaster, Fleury & Fleury, 2017). The performance of cross-border logistics has also been investigated to measure how well the business is doing in each activity. Six logistics performance indexes can calculate logistics performance analysis in international trade, including (1) ability to track and trace consignments, (2) competence and quality of logistics services, (3) ease of arranging competitively priced shipments, (4) efficiency of the customs clearance process, (5) frequency which shipment reach consignee within scheduled or expected time and (6) quality of trade and transport-related infrastructure. The results from Gani (2017), which focused on the role that logistics plays in supporting the activities within an economy, provide strong evidence of the positive role that logistics plays in increasing trade. However, every organization, whether a manufacturer, wholesale, or retailer, buys materials, services, and supplies to support the operations. Without reliable providers, the most commercial activity could not function, and the trade could not exist (Bowersox et al., 2013). Therefore, the importance of competencies, skills and knowledge of the providers should not be ignored as they are more likely the key players of cross-border operation.

The study done by Vaičiute, Skirmantiene and Domanska (2017) investigated three components for competencies of the key players in the cross-border process, which are competencies of transport management specialists, executives' attitudes and skills and capabilities that match with the ability or competencies to operate cross-border logistic because transportation cost represents the number of products to be carried using route by lorry are paid in term of order (Leung, Wu, & Lai, 2002). Suppose an organization understand the current trade labour situations. In that case, they should rethink human resource strategies and react to changes due to rapid changes and diversity in the labour force and the labour movement. Moreover, cross-border cooperation and border traffic Border formalities are also significantly affected by the action of border traffic (Studzieniecki, Palmowski & Korneevets, 2016).

Unless the hiring cost of product delivery, inventory cost for storing of excess products in ware become the efficiency barriers while the allowance or an extra paid for related people also become cost reduction that has been proved by the findings of the study from Leung et al., (2002) which mentioned that the cost could save 75% of efficiency operations especially in transportation cost. The findings from the research on the value chain of timber from Myanmar to China studied by Dong, and He (2018) found that countries with import-export relations influence the high or low efficiency of operations in each activity.

Table 1

Summary of previous studies on Cross-border logistics problems

Author & Year	Problem	Concerned
Vaičiute et al. (2017)	Competencies of staffs concerned cross-border operation	Operations/ Logistics service provider
Studzieniecki et al.(2016)	Cross-border operations in tourism development	Operations
Leung et al. (2002)	Cross-border efficiency problem	Operations
Pinto et al. (2017)	The role of government support in ownership in cross-border acquisitions (CBAs)	Operations/ Government administration
Gani (2017)	Performance of logistics in oversea trade based logistics	Operations/ Logistics service provider/ Government administration
Dong and He (2018)	Import-export value & supply chain	Operations/ Logistics service provider/ Government administration

The problems illustrated in Table 1 are concerned with cross-border operations, logistics service providers and government administration. The most mentioned issue involved processes at the border area, especially for trading performed by logistics service providers and government administration.

5. Enhancement of Cross-border Logistics toward Global Supply Chain

Evidence from many empirical studies, the cross-border operations, had been investigated from a different perspective with various contexts. Their primary purposes are to reduce barriers and increase cross-border operations capabilities in many operational cross-border types, such as cross-border tourism, cross-border e-commerce, cross-border mobility, and cross-border logistics. From the analysis of overall findings, most studies found that the development of trading, services, and movement of merchandises in cross-border operations are relevant and required cooperation from many different players. (Bochaton, 2015; Studzieniecki et al., 2016; Pinto et al., 2017)

The first prioritized sector mentioned when discussing border crossing is "government"(Río, Agüera, Cuadra & Morales 2017; Yilmaz & Bititci, 2006). Firstly, the government is majorly referred to as a critical player in creating policies and regulations in operations. Therefore, the flexible and transparent practices from the government are taken as excellent opportunities for making smooth operations cross-border. Secondly, the government is a leading supportive organization of establishing necessary facilities to create a more convenient flow of activities and cross-border operations. For example, the infrastructure development may improve border traffic area and bring new technology tools to eliminate working steps and complexities to increase efficiency in both cost and time reduction taken in the operations. Finally, the government is responsible for creating cooperation on many different levels, such as regional, national, and international levels, supporting border-crossing activities to be more facilitated, faster, and higher of efficient. Besides, many researchers have significantly investigated the speed and efficiency of the operation as they are important drivers to develop the operation process of border crossing.

The efficiency in cross-border operation occurs when unnecessary costs and procedures for implementation are removed, and the value delivered to customers is added. The improvement of documents used for border crossing in the context of the movement of products, services, and people can be helpful by reducing cross-border operations, fewer customs clearance and document declaration processes, and reduced dwell time of merchandised movement. To improve all procedures mentioned above is aligned with the concept of minimum cost with high value. Working in this way provides better operations efficiency and the acquisitions of economic value that support and promote the country in international progress.

The factors that should not be ignored to improve cross-border operations fostering up efficiency, are the specific knowledge and skills of the performers (Vaičiute et al., 2017). Some researchers found that all players such as manufacturers, wholesale, retailer, buyers, services, suppliers, and others are concerned about supporting cross-border operations (Dong & He, 2018). Therefore, those must be fulfilled with the necessary knowledge and skills for implementation to enable cross-border operations. For instance, they need to understand clearly the knowledge about logistics, formalities and operation process. Also, the skills of cooperation and communication are essential for them to which they should be able to communicate in foreign languages because it is precisely more than one countries of working in term of cross-border operations especially the fluency of English communication due to it can reduce trade barrier and improve cross-border efficiency with faster performance and lower mistakes. Thus, it is essential for the organization associated with operational cross-border to carefully analyze necessary knowledge and skills for working and develop staff competencies and capabilities to meet and align with the actual needs (Vaičiute et al., 2017).

The improvement of border crossing operation, as mentioned above, impacts the results in terms of time and cost reduction. The quality of the outcome may lead to the effectiveness of cross-border operations to encourage the country's economy and among the region. The quality of cross-border implementation can be measured in many different approaches. For example, to evaluate customer satisfaction as a user of border crossing process in various contexts such as cross-border tourism (Studzieniecki et al., 2016) and cross-border mobility (Koran, 2015), to measure the performance in the operational cross-border by using an international standard indicator such as using logistics performance index to identify the competency in the process of cross-border logistics (Gani, 2017; Su & Ke, 2017) to fostering up more efficient and increase the growth of the economy, society, and community in the same time.

The World Bank (2019) summarized the approaches of cross-border operations improvement categorized by the three main criteria of making it easier to trade across borders. Firstly, the initiation of electronic submission and documents improvement processing for import and export. An example of practical approaches includes Kazakhstan introducing an electronic customs declaration system and reducing customs administration fees. Uganda had a full implementation of centralized documents checking platforms using an electronic system such as the "Uganda Electronic Single Window," which provided document submission and information exchange via the electronic system. Moreover, the trader in Lesotho reduced the time of documents checking for import by an automatic system for customs data. In Paraguay, an electronic signature for commercial operations had been certified as legally valid.

Secondly, improving infrastructure could reinforce the border for import and export. Some highlights approach for improving infrastructure, which mostly resulted in time and process reduction, such as El Salvador established new customs posts in Santa Ana to reduce the congestion of border crossing in the main post at Anguiatu. Also, Rwanda implemented the Single Customs Territory, which arranged more staff to operate a

one-stop border post and reduced time. Additionally, Malaysia cut off time by expanding a new gate at Port Klang with a modern management system, more scanner, and two terminals.

Thirdly, the enhancement of administration and inspection in customs for imports and exports. For example, In Mauritius, fourteen hours were cut in border compliance by implementing risk-based management. Ukraine eliminated the requirement in auto-parts verification. The operations in Kosovo were simplified border control and the physical examination process of customs clearance.

Table 2 indicated the components of effective operations for trading across the border, including 1) electronic processing system, 2) infrastructure development, and 3) improvement of customs inspection. These three components impact the entire procedures, as the example shown in Table 2. These three components will be discussed later as a variable affecting the functional performance of cross-border operations.

Table 2

Important approaches of cross-border operations improvement

Feature	Some highlights
Initiation of electronic submission and documents improvement processing for export	Kazakhstan:Electronic customs declaration system Uganda:Centralized documents checking platform by using an electronic system called "Uganda Electronic Single Window".
Initiation of electronic submission and documents improvement processing for import	Lesotho: Automatic system for custom data Paraguay: Certifylegal validity of electronic signature for commercial operations
Infrastructure reinforcement of border for export	EL Salvador: New customs post established in Santa Ana Rwanda: Single Customs Territory, with more staff to operate one-stop border post
Infrastructure reinforcement of border for import	Malaysia: Expand a new gate at Port Klang with a modern management system, more scanner and two terminals.
Enhancement of administration and inspection in customs for imports and exports	Mauritius: Risk-based management implementation Ukraine:Fewer requirements in auto-parts verification. Kosovo:Simplified border control and physical examination process of customs clearance.

Source: The World Bank (2019)

Limitations

Even if the main purpose of this study which is to explain how cross-border logistics is essential in the global supply chain, was accomplished. This study also has its limitation. First, the results have not presented the relationship and the connection between cross-border logistics contributing to the global value chain. Especially, the logistics service providers and the government are the key players in processing cross-border logistics operations. Second, there should be investigated factors that enhance the capability to provide international logistics services to the providers and the practical management approaches or resources necessary for improving government roles in facilitating logistics operations which the practitioners could have the ideas or strategies to develop their performance. Moreover, it would be indicators for import-export business to evaluate the service providers and decide to select the service providers that most provide minimum cost with high quality of service. This fulfilment would generate value in the global supply chain, straightening the economy among geographic regions. Finally, the study area should be specific due to different areas face different problems and players, which will be more effective to bring the concepts gained in the study to apply for the actual practice.

Conclusion

The complexity and strict rules for cross-border trade continually disrupt the efficiency and competitive advantage of business nowadays. Thus, this study explicitly mentions two significant players who handle cross-border logistics operations. First, the logistics service providers (LSP) are concerned with a slow process of logistics operating, delayed delivery, and sometimes the problem of unqualified staff to provide international logistics services. The second is the processes implemented by government administration, for instance, the declaration, document submission, trade facilities(both physical and tangible), infrastructures, trade policies and limited competency of staff. Therefore, the components of effective operations for global supply chain contribution, including electronic processing system, infrastructure development and improvement of customs inspection.

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